

LIMNOLOGY OF DRYLANDS WG

International Network on Limnology of Drylands (INLD)

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Currently, climate change and the human-domain are the main drivers of changes in aquatic ecosystems across the world. In anthropogenic scenarios, warmer climates, overexploitation, nutrients enrichment and other drivers may induce irreversible shifts in these ecosystems, mainly in dry zones. Aquatic ecosystems have a great ecological and economic relevance in arid and semiarid zones, useful for irrigation and other economic activities, essential to the livelihood of 2.1 billion people (Reid *et al.*, 2005. Millenium Ecosystem Assessment. UNEP).

Since its creation, the greatest challenge of the International Network on Limnology of Drylands (INLD) is the reconciliation of conservation and sustainable development of these zones. During the last decade, extreme and prolonged droughts arising as one of the main consequences of anthropogenic climate change (Marvel *et al.*, 2019. Nature 569: 59-65) have negatively influenced the biodiversity and resilience of water bodies. Therefore, research and experiments will be carried out aiming to understand the effects of local stressors and consequences of increasing temperature on these ecosystems.

Group Meeting had a special focus on the actions developed between 2020 and 2021 (Fig. 1b). Among the proposals for future actions, researchers highlighted the importance of establishing a common field protocol to be used by the members in all countries, mainly in lentic ecosystems. Colleagues from Brazil, Spain, Egypt, Denmark, Germany, Ecuador, Russia, India, among others, were present. The protocol is being prepared and is strictly associated with the main objectives of INLD: i) to assess the current state of biological diversity in dryland aquatic ecosystems; ii) to evaluate multiple environmental stressors; iii) to develop predictive models to estimate the effects of global changes on drylands. The expectation is to answer the main threats associated with biodiversity in drylands.

Currently, the main projects of INLD prioritize the study of local pressures and global warming and their potential effects on aquatic biodiversity and water quality, including scientometric and meta-analysis studies in global dryland freshwater ecosystems, aiming to identify trends in temporal and spatial scales. Other projects underway have a special focus on a *space for time* approach: i) Galapagos program: Iconic Galapagos aquatic ecosystems as a climate change hot-spot? (Fig. 1c, e), ii) Rockpools (and temporary ecosystems) in world drylands (Fig. 1d, f), iii) Phosphorus cycling in aquatic ecosystems in drylands regions.

Fig. 1 a) Eduardo Vicente (University of Valencia) and Luciana Barbosa (Chair of INLD); **b)** Special Session “Ecology and conservation of temporary aquatic ecosystems” in the 36th Congress of the International Society of Limnology (SIL2022); **c)** El Junco lake (Galapagos National Park, San Cristobal Island); **d)** Rock pools (Northeast of Brazil); **e)** Sampling in Galapagos lakes with Miriam Steinitz- Kannan, José Carlos Lopez (Co-chair of INLD) and Raúl Tomalá; **f)** Arch Lagoon, a temporary lake in the Namib desert (Angola).

Regarding the activities of this WG, in 2021 and 2022 some actions were carried out in Brazil, Portugal, Spain, Germany and Ecuador. In the 2nd meeting of the Iberian Ecological Society (SIBECOL) and the XXI conference of the Iberian Association of Limnology (AIL), the special session *Ecology and conservation of temporary aquatic ecosystems* was conducted by Luciana Barbosa (INLD) and Maximo Floriano Florin (University of Castilla-La Mancha, Spain). In this session presentations from Spain, Brazil and Portugal were made, with special focus on biodiversity and the potential effects of climate change and human pressures in iconic ecosystems, such as the aquatic ecosystems of Doñana State Park (Spain). Furthermore, technical visits were made in Portugal and Spain aiming to expand actions and research lines of INLD. In Evora (Portugal), discussions revolved around advances in research projects and scientific papers, associated with biodiversity and ecological redundancy as well as new perspectives in drylands zones. In Spain, the main action was strengthening partnerships with researchers from Valencia University (Fig.1a). One of our main objectives was to identify new perspectives and approaches to improve investigations in drylands zones.

During the 36th Congress of the International Society of Limnology (SIL2022) in Germany, INLD held a special session *Ecology and conservation of temporary aquatic ecosystems*, coordinated by Luciana Barbosa, Carlos López (INLD) and Rachel Stubbington (Nottingham Trent University). This session featured presentations from Brazil, Spain, India, Australia, Ecuador and the United Kingdom. The official Working

Overall, our goal is to identify trends and emphasize the vulnerability of these dynamic and highly diverse ecosystems. With this in mind, we expect to be at the forefront of combating climate change through a better comprehension of arid systems and by providing advances for the conservation of aquatic ecosystems in drylands zones.

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